

15th European congress for Paediatric Anaesthesiology
2–4 October 2025, Berlin, Germany

THE CRITICAL ROLE OF BEDSIDE ULTRASOUND (POCUS) IN SEVERE PEDIATRIC LIVER TRAUMA: A CASE REPORT

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Introduction: Liver injuries in childhood account approximately 5% of all emergency admissions. Liver trauma diagnosis includes physical examination, focused assessment sonography for trauma (FAST) and CT. FAST is a rapid bedside POCUS (point of care ultrasound) for detection of hemopericardium, hemopneumothorax and free intraperitoneal fluid.

Case description: A 12 years old female patient after bicycle collision was admitted with satisfying respiratory status, normotensive and tachycardic. POCUS- FAST and CT were done and diagnosis of liver rupture grade V was made based on hepatic injury scale. Initial treatment considered non-operative management. The laboratory tests showed anaemia and initial blood glucose level 45 mmol/l. Crystalloid infusions, red blood cells and short acting human insulin were administered. Few hours later patient became hemodynamically unstable, when repeated POCUS confirmed massive intraabdominal haemorrhage and the patient was intubated and transported into the operating room. Liver tamponade and drainage of abdominal cavity was performed, and POCUS echocardiography showed acute heart insufficiency. Inotropic support with dobutamine was used during next 6 days and vasoactive therapy with norepinephrine during next 3 days. Three days after admission serum creatinine began to rise, patient became oligoanuric and abdominal POCUS verified hyperechoic changes of kidneys. Eight days after admission, CVVHDF was performed during 24 hours, and repeated 4 days after. Patient was intubated during 14 days, and discharged after 28 days to general surgical ward in good general condition.

Discussion: Mortality rate in patients with severe hepatic trauma amounts 10-15%. Almost all patients with liver trauma can be treated by non-operative management. In cases of verified hemodynamic instability, FAST can be of great benefit in the assesment of necessity of operative treatment. In eight prospective studies, FAST has been shown to have 35% sensitivity and 96% specificity and is a cardinal method for assessment, although it shouldn't be interpreted independently.

References:

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